

Reflecting lifelong learning in multipurpose electronic portfolios

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“Life is the sum of all your choices.” Albert Camus

Introduction

Learning, the accumulation of all one's experiences, continues as long as we are living. Studies have shown that we learn even when asleep (Koninck, Christ, Hebert, & Rinfret, 1990).

Individuals naturally enjoy reflecting on their accumulated experiences, as evidenced amply in personal Web sites, photograph albums, journals, and scrapbooks as well as more formal curriculum vitae, portfolios, autobiographies, and memoirs. One could never completely list a lifetime's activities. Even if available, that exhaustive inventory would not predict clearly which combined experiences from all activities have resulted in knowledge and skills for new endeavors. Therefore, we have to choose and prioritize our experiences to draw conclusions about them. Well-selected descriptions of experience can support lifelong learning. This article describes how to construct electronic portfolios so they enhance the process.

Portfolio construction

A portfolio, as a tool to support learning, is the result of a cyclic process in which one enters data on life experiences, analyzes those data, draws conclusions, and plan new activities. That cycle is reflected in the five steps of portfolio construction described below.

Step 1. Selecting personal projects

Portfolio construction starts by grouping related activities into meaningful units or *personal projects*. Such projects can highlight formal learning (a course), work (managing a department for a few years), and other aspects of life (raising kids). The selection of personal projects is a choice based on ideas about what kind of project descriptions might be useful for future reference. A major issue is the aggregation level used for a personal project (like whether to describe a course or a study in one project). The choice reflects a trade-off between limiting the number of projects and limiting information loss. Typically, young people select a lower aggregation level than older adults, especially if the list of personal projects has to cover an entire lifetime. The aggregation level / time span can vary among projects; more detailed levels will be chosen for projects with greater potential for future use. Often those are the recent projects like present courses at school or work done for companies the last year. Organizations might request the use of certain standard personal projects (e.g., course assignments or annual professional development projects in a company).

Step 2. Describing personal projects

In constructing a portfolio, one describes personal projects in terms of *goal, process, and results*. Goals are formulated in terms of a new situation that can only be reached by performing certain activities. *Process* descriptions might include details of the activities, especially if those activities have potential relevance for future use. *Results* might be both quantitative and qualitative (e.g., recommendation letters and testimonials made by others).

The descriptions of personal projects become the information core of an electronic portfolio. This information core describes learning results and provides the basis for *personal reflections*.

Step 3. Adding personal reflections

Personal reflections are short personal analyses of activities, processes, or results. Based both on observation and on personal judgments, these initial reflections can help an individual choose which information to include within each personal project. At a different level, one may add reflections on the entire portfolio (multiple project level) to formulate a personal development plan within the portfolio. This reflection might address key questions in life, although it typically addresses the audience who will next review the electronic portfolio. For example, a teacher's personal development plan might mention competencies still to be mastered with a reflection about the teacher's preferred instructional approaches. In the workplace, a personal development plan might be reviewed at intervals with one's supervisor or mentor, to evaluate and plan professional development.

Step 4. Adding competency descriptions and captions

Competency descriptions can enhance the portfolio if one needs to prove the attainment of particular standards. These competency descriptions should be copied from a well-established source, so that the portfolio reviewer will recognize them. Each competency should state performance criterion (the kind and level of evidence needed to document mastery). For each criterion, the person involved will describe the evidence by (a) pointing to information within the personal projects and (b) explaining why that information proves mastery. That evidence explanation will be referred to as a *caption*.

Step 5. Formulating a (new) personal development plan

The overview of personal projects (steps 1 and 2), reflections (step 3), and the (self-) assessment (step 4) provide a good basis to make new plans for personal development. In a work environment, the personal development plan can provide the individual basis for professional development planned in companies. In a school situation, fixed parts of the curriculum might provide a framework for the personal development plan. Within that framework personal goals and choices are formulated as new personal projects. In a self-controlled learning situation, the personal development plan provides the basis to explicitly plan, monitor and evaluate learning.

Underlying principles of portfolio construction

When constructing an electronic portfolio, it is important to keep a few principles in mind.

1 Separation of personal project data from the competency descriptions

When the portfolio contains competency descriptions, learning information should not be grouped with these descriptions but stored within the personal projects, the universal information core of the electronic portfolio. The captions draw the connection between evidence in the personal projects and the mastery of competencies. Technology is particularly helpful in making these connections. In a word processor, a learner can connect the projects and the competencies with a bookmark and reference tools; in a web-based portfolio, the same connection can be made with hyperlinks. This approach has a few important advantages:

- the portfolio can be used for more than one set of competencies.
- the same personal project information can be linked to different captions proving different competencies.
- it enables reflection on portfolio (multiple projects) level
- it makes it easy to find and select evidence for a new set of competencies
- it makes it easy to store new evidence even if that is not needed yet for the competencies sets that are presently under consideration
- it enables direct use of the personal project information like for showing and reusing results

2 Analyses based on reflection is essential

Electronic Portfolios support learning by the analyses made in their construction and use. These analyses start at a low level in the first two steps of portfolio construction as decisions are made on useful personal project descriptions. However, the real learning support comes from higher-level analyses made through reflection resulting in new ideas or plans. If the portfolio is used to prove mastery of competency, then the analyses made in the captions show the value of the personal project data.

3 Proper use of three levels of information selection and presentation

It is useful to have a working directory on a disk drive for each selected personal project. On such a directory all kind of material related to the personal project is stored. It can even be the directory on which the daily work for that project is done. The only selection criterion for storage of material in these directories is the possible need for any future reference. Each directory is linked to a personal project description of the multipurpose portfolio constructed in the steps described above. The directories serve as a general-purpose *archive* and the combination of that archive with a multipurpose portfolio can be seen as a *portfolio system* (Wielenga, 2001). The multipurpose portfolio represents the second level of information presentation that can be used to generate third level selections aimed at specific audiences. This third level equals that of a single purpose portfolio. The three levels are connected by the use of the same personal project structure that enables efficient (re) use of information.

4 The portfolio is controlled by the individual involved

Part of the information in the electronic portfolio might be very private; such as self-reflection on failure. These parts will never be developed if the entire portfolio has to be shown to the world to reach potential employers or customers. The individual involved must be in control of the use of the portfolio information. She/he must have the facilities and rights to restrict information access to any part of the portfolio in any desired way. Sometimes, joining organizations might set limits for the individual in the use of these rights. An elegant way to achieve personal control and organizational use is to construct the first two levels of the portfolio on a personal disk drive. From that, third level selections can be uploaded to the systems of the organization(s) involved. Work on the portfolio is as much as possible done on the multipurpose portfolio (second level) and as far as it has to be done on the third level the results of that are downloaded to the second level at intervals.

Purposes of multipurpose electronic portfolios

Portfolios constructed and organized according to the guidelines on the previous pages can foster learning and recognition of competency in almost any way mentioned in literature for portfolios with specific purposes (Lankes, 1998; Niguidula, 1997; Wolf, 1999; Milman, 1999). Multipurpose portfolios can be useful in many ways:

1. Self-directed learning, key competencies, and self-esteem

The descriptions of personal projects and activities can contain explicit formulations of goals, plans, and reflections on process and results. Creating and editing those formulations, helps to reach higher level / metacognitive learning. It aids learners to self-direct their learning promotes essential competencies like learning to learn, interpersonal, and team skills, problem-solving, and information literacy. Moreover, this process can increase self-efficacy (Pajares & Schunk, 2001) Self-directed learning, key competencies, and self-esteem are essential in any work environment.

2. Personal development planning

The use of a portfolio enables personal development planning to be based on explicit descriptions of experience within personal projects, reflections on a single and multi personal project level, and the results of (self)-assessment. This provides a high-quality basis to set new goals and make new choices. Within the portfolio, those choices can be formulated in terms of new personal projects which enables monitoring of the results and the formulation of reflections on those results. This cyclic use of a portfolio is an excellent way to support and evaluate personal development planning.

3. General stimulation of learning

The explicit descriptions of activities and projects in the electronic portfolio are both a starting point and a target for new learning activities. Existing experience descriptions can be reused and refined in new learning activities. This reflects the essence of learning according to modern views like constructivist learning; (Tam, 2000). Also, the use of an electronic portfolio ensures the learner that the outcome of a learning project will never be lost. That provides a basic motivation to be involved in new learning activities and to reach high-quality results.

4. Proving of competence

Proof of competence can be achieved by comparing a relevant selection of personal project data with performance criteria for the competence involved. This comparison can be limited to the self-assessment formulated in the captions. Also, external validation can be done by a qualified assessor, this is usually done by discussing the captions and if needed observing simulations or performance in a relevant situation.

5. Showing competencies and qualifications to potential employers, colleagues, and potential customers

Presenting one's self to potential employers, colleagues and potential clients is a traditional use for portfolios. Portfolios help them to recognize the competencies and quality of the candidate. Companies might require these presentations to prove that their personnel meets the standards required for certain projects or positions.

6. Reflecting on personal growth

Many people feel the need to show parts of their life to themselves, their relatives, friends, and the world in the form of personal web pages. Authors of personal web pages might be highly motivated to maintain an electronic portfolio. If they learn to use the right structures and to analyze by reflection, their passion for presenting themselves on the web might foster their learning

Using an electronic portfolio lifelong

Initially, a portfolio might be constructed with a certain purpose in mind, and in that situation, time limitations might require to describe only those personal projects with high relevance for that purpose. Such a portfolio might neglect the results of informal learning, but it can be a practical first step and the multipurpose setup will allow personal project data to be extended later.

A multipurpose electronic portfolio can remain in use even if the need to serve specific purposes shifts during life. This will motivate to construct an electronic portfolio during initial education, and eliminate the need of building a series of different portfolios in lifetime. Also, it will support longer-term reflection.

Informal learning

Using an electronic portfolio lifelong also justifies the large efforts needed to describe informal learning within the personal projects. This is important, as a personal development plan can't be formulated properly without recognition of the results of informal learning. The results of informal learning might be taken into account through an official accreditation procedure including formal assessment or self-assessment as shown below:

Use of one portfolio within several organizations

In a lifetime, individuals are members of several organizations like schools and companies; and these organizations differ in what they would expect regarding content, structure, and techniques of the portfolios. A well-designed personal project structure with separation of the personal project data from competency descriptions will enable transfer from one technique to another as well as provide flexible information presentation. It is therefore important that organizations and individuals agree on a standardized electronic portfolio structure based on these principles. When electronic portfolios are used to prove competencies, standardized descriptions and criteria of those competencies should be imported from certified sources as this will result in wide recognition. In the future, the information fields within an electronic portfolio can be made accessible for systems of an organization by using extensions of information standards like IMS Learner Information Package Specification (Smythe, Tansey, & Robson, 2001). This will not only aid the transfer of information between the electronic portfolio and the systems of organizations but also help in finding information within an electronic portfolio containing large amounts of information. Of course, the basis for automatic information exchange will have to be an agreement between the individual and the organization about what kind of information can be transferred.

Conclusion

The stepwise construction approach and the use of underlying principles described in this article will dramatically improve any portfolio. The only significant additional effort compared to the construction of a traditional single-purpose portfolio comes from the introduction of the multipurpose portfolio level between the hard disk data and the portfolio presented to a specific audience. However, this step is useful in a single-purpose portfolio as well as it allows the individual to have a complete portfolio for his/herself while parts of that portfolio are available to different audiences.

Electronic portfolios require considerable effort, made worthwhile by the lifelong opportunities to use one's information to support professional as well as personal growth.

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